

Script Interview 2025

Appendix of the article titled “A Quality Assurance Perspective of Fairness Evaluation for ML-enabled Systems”.

This interview script is based on the Seven-Layered Model proposed by Agarwal et al. [1]. Below, we present the questions from the model we used in the interviews.

- Layer 1 - Requirements, Context, and Purpose: Aims to assess the problem understanding and requirements elicitation stage. It does not involve data handling, but it is also important for developing a fair system.
 - What are the expectations from the AI model?
 - Are the requirements clear and formally documented?
 - Have the developers understood the scope and context of the problem?
 - How is the problem being dealt with presently?
 - Which fairness technique is appropriate and why?
 - How are the tolerance limits for fairness and bias decided?
 - Was the relevant AI literature reviewed
 - Is the data generated internally or from external third-party/ public sources?
 - Were benchmarks and baselines identified?
 - Are Pre-trained models already available that can be repurposed?
 - What are the alternate solutions and flows?
 - Are the stakeholders, domain experts, and auditors identified?
 - Does the stakeholder group have a proportionate representation of all demographic groups that might be affected by this model?
 - Were fairness-related potential harms identified and discussed?
 - Who would be the beneficiaries of this model and will it negatively affect any group/ individual?
 - Are there any relevant standards, policies, or guidelines?
 - Have all the project members had ethical training or attended workshops/courses concerning AI ethics?

- Layer 2 - Data collection and selection: Concerns activities for data collection. It involves identifying data sources, creating a data collection protocol, and labeling according to the defined problem.
 - Is there a way to audit the dataset for validity and accuracy?
 - Is the dataset complete? Are there too many missing values?
 - Is the dataset cleaned and pre-processed or raw?
 - How distributed is the dataset? Does it include data from all sections of society? Is it skewed in favour of certain groups?

- Is there any metadata available along with the dataset that increases its explainability? Is the information available about who collected it, when it was collected, and the collection processes used?
- Why was this data collected?
- How old is the dataset? Do the situations/assumptions at the time of data collection still apply?
- Is more than one dataset being considered? If yes, what is the correlation between them?
- Are all the attributes in the dataset legally approved for use?
- Is the dataset already labelled?
- In the case of manual labelling, are the people labelling the data trained and well aware of the context of the problem?
- Are quality assurance and verification processes included to ensure no developer bias gets into the dataset?
- Layer 3 - Data Pre-processing and Feature Engineering: Aims at evaluating data pre-processing and feature engineering. Most datasets used for training models require pre-processing. The same dataset can be used to train different models for various problems.
 - What are the approaches taken to clean the dataset? Are they leading to an imbalanced dataset?
 - How is feature engineering done? Was it done by a single developer or reviewed by others also?
 - Were any features dropped? If yes, why and what effect do they have on the problem?
 - Would the pre-processing process remove an enormous chunk of data from a particular demography?
 - As part of over-sampling, did the algorithm add too much synthetic data?
 - How were the normalisation and scaling techniques decided?
 - How were the protected attributes and privileged classes selected?
- Layer 4 - Algorithm: The questions relate to evaluating the model development. It involves choosing the model type, the algorithm, the fairness criteria, and the model coding.
 - Is the development process transparent?
 - Are there regular reviews and quality assessments in the organisation to check that the developers' individual biases do not influence their work?
 - What were the criteria for selecting the algorithm technique?
 - Were the stakeholders consulted? Was the context of the problem statement taken into consideration?
 - Which fairness technique was selected—individual fairness, group fairness, or something else?
 - Is the model developed per the requirements specified in layer 1?

- Layer 5 - AI System Training: Focuses on evaluating the model training stage and all related activities, including splitting the dataset, training the model iteratively, and evaluating it using various metrics, including fairness metrics.
 - How was the dataset divided into training, testing, and validation sets? Was the data distributed to them randomly?
 - Were the resultant three datasets balanced? Did they have an equal/proportional distribution of privileged and unprivileged classes?
 - How were the hyper-parameters selected?
 - What are the fairness metrics used, and why?
 - Is fairness checked for each protected attribute or not?
 - What are the identified benchmarks, parameters, and metrics for measuring model performance, and why?
 - The choice of metrics, parameters, and benchmarks should be well documented and available for external auditing and explainability.
- Layer 6 - Independent Audit Layer: The goal is to determine whether fairness testing and certification are performed by a team separate from the developers. This stage involves an independent evaluation of the various fairness metrics used in layer five and independent auditors.
 - Is the auditor independent? If it is an in-house team, then is it different from the developers? If it is a third-party auditor, then is it accredited?
 - Is a standard fairness assessment process followed?

References:

[1] Avinash Agarwal and Harsh Agarwal. 2024. A seven-layer model with checklists for standardising fairness assessment throughout the AI lifecycle. In AI and Ethics. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-023-00266-9>